

To: The Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

From: E [REDACTED] C [REDACTED]

Subject: Memorandum Opposing the “Promotion of Proper Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill” (2021)

Date: September 30, 2021

POSITION:

I am writing as a Ghanaian of the diaspora who has been coming home regularly for almost thirty years. I oppose the draft bill which distorts “family values” to justify violence against Ghanaians on the basis of gender, sexual identity, and political opinions. The bill contains several elements that endorse targeted punishment of LGBTQI people and their allies, which is both implicitly and explicitly prohibited by the constitution.

INTRODUCTION:

Four features of this bill directly contravene the protections enshrined in Ghana’s constitution. Yet for some, the moral tone has disguised the most dangerous and discriminatory consequences. The combined effect of 1) pathologizing laws, 2) conversion therapy, 3) gender “normalization” surgery, and 4) punishment of LGBTQI rights advocacy will deepen discrimination, rupture families, increase public health challenges, and roll back democratic engagement while compromising Ghana’s reputation in the diaspora. In what follows I take the elements of the bill by turn to urge evaluation based on its consequences rather than its superficial claim to support “family values”.

PATHOLOGIZING LAWS

In 2016, the African Commission on Human and People’s Rights issued a statement against the pathologization of LGBT¹ adults and children, citing this practice as the root cause of violence and discrimination, specifically “abusive, harmful, and unethical forced treatments” that lead to “preventable early deaths”.² State policies that attempt to alter and criminalize LGBTQI people sanction far-reaching discrimination and provoke violence, which opposes Ghana’s constitutional obligation to support the “fundamental dignity of the human.”³

If allowed, this development could turn every form of contact with government agencies and religious worship into an opportunity for policing and discrimination. Ghanaians will avoid using necessary services or joining religious organizations if there is a risk of discrimination on the basis of perceived gender or sexual orientation. Though sexual orientation is not a protected status in Ghana, the constitution promises to prevent class-based discrimination. For LGBTQI people who cannot afford legal representation or lack social networks that help them avoid prison, this bill effectively yields a class-specific outcome.

¹ The memo refers to LGBT and Intersex people separately.

² African Commission on Human and People’s Rights, “Pathologization: being lesbian, gay, bisexual and/or trans is not an illness,” Press Release (May 12, 2016).

³ Constitution of the Republic of Ghana (1993, amended 1996), Article 35.

In addition to the promotion of violence and class-based policing, this bill legitimates family rejection, increasing the potential for suicide among LGBTQI youth especially. Family conflict is the leading reason for suicidal ideation in Ghana.⁴ Compounded by workplace discrimination, LGBTQI youth are uniquely vulnerable to suicidal thinking and actions when faced with an impossible demand for conformity.

CONDITIONAL INCLUSION

This bill also sidesteps a constitutional commitment to an inclusive society by punishing those who do not accept “conversion” therapy. A debunked therapeutic practice, conversion therapy has survived mainly through conservative Christian sponsors and media attention, not through evidence-based research on gender diversity and sexual orientation.⁵ Conversion therapy has been discredited so thoroughly, that specific churches have become the primary sources of clientele for therapists operating outside of professional guidelines. As a result, many denominations have issued statements to break the association between religion and conversion therapy.⁶ In 2018, the American Psychiatric Association cited the harm caused by conversion therapy as a leading contributor to suicide and stress-related illnesses induced by the pressure to disguise internal desires for the sake of social conformity. Prison cannot redeem conversion therapy, though this bill attempts to leverage prison to reboot a failed technique in Ghana.

THE ARBITRARINESS OF GENDER “NORMALIZATION” SURGERY

If the stress of conversion therapy and imprisonment causes long-term harm, what of the proposal to use gender “normalization” surgery for intersex children? This bill endorses cosmetic surgery on children’s genitalia to make naturally occurring chromosomal differences conform to a binary view of gender. With no access to speech, intersex infants cannot communicate their gender identity prior to surgery, leading doctors to guess. Such guess work threatens psychological dissonance from the combination of surgery and social pressure to perform the gender assigned at birth.⁷ Ghana’s constitution protects “developmental processes” which includes a child’s gender development.⁸ Because the constitution explicitly prohibits discrimination related to circumstances of birth, parliament must oppose arbitrary genital surgery in service of social conformity.

⁴ Quarshie, et al. “Adolescent Suicide in Ghana: A Content Analysis of Media Reports,” *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-Being* 10:1 (2015); Owusu Ansah, et al. “Suicide Among University Students: Prevalence, Risk and Protective Factors,” *Health Psychology and Behavioral Medicine* 8:1 (2020), 220-233; Osafo, et al. “Attempted Suicide in Ghana: Motivation, Stigma, and Coping,” *Death Studies* 39:5 (2015) 274-280.

⁵ In 2020, the United Nations issued a call for a global end to conversion therapy. In a report on the effects of “conversion” the report demonstrated numerous fraudulent claims and practices that “amount to torture.” Victor Madrigal-Borloz, “Practices of so-called Conversion Therapy,” Forty-fourth session of the Human Rights Council (July 2020), 15-16.

⁶ The Roman Catholic Church, Methodist, and United Church of Christ, in addition to many smaller denominations, have opposed conversion therapy around the world. While some Pentacostal and Baptist denominations continue to support it against the grain of research and legal sanction in many countries.

⁷ Kishka Kamari Ford, “First Do No Harm: The Fiction of Legal Parental Consent to Gender-Normalizing Surgery on Intersexed Infants,” *Yale Law and Policy Review* 19:2 (2001), 469-488.

⁸ Articles 28 and 37.

PUNISHING ADVOCACY

The bill not only argues for the punishment of people with diverse genders or sexual orientations, it targets anyone who speaks about it. The bill threatens to imprison people who advocate for LGBTQI rights. This despite an explicit prohibition on imprisonment for political opinions.⁹ The constitution protects freedom of speech, association, and organization. And yet, in January 2021 the Accra LGBTQI resource center was raided by police forces with barely a chance to hold initial meetings. Following the raid, this bill was drafted to permanently strip Ghanaian citizens of the right “to form their own associations, free from state interference,” projecting violence onto the group—when in fact, the group was violated.¹⁰ Projection cannot be the basis of law. We need to prevent this poorly argued attempt to undermine constitutional rights. Vote no.

⁹ Articles 21, 35, and 55.

¹⁰ The draft bill cites the Vigilantism and Related Offenses Act (2019) to accuse the LGBTQI group of organizing by threat, even though the office was forcibly closed by police and this bill is organized by threats of imprisonment, social exclusion, and compulsory surgery.